

Rac-1ah

SAMPLE INFORMATION			
Sample Name:	xt-2-75-2-s-RAC-20%-AD	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name:	
Vial:	7	Acq. Method Set:	20%qb
Injection #:	1	Processing Method:	XT 2 75 2 S RAC
Injection Volume:	10.00 ul	Channel Name:	254.0nm
Run Time:	60.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 254.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	1/21/2022 11:24:11 AM CST		
Date Processed:	1/21/2022 2:59:52 PM CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	4.867	3820173	49.74	494249
2	5.716	3859991	50.26	423011

Asy-1ah

SAMPLE INFORMATION			
Sample Name:	xt-2-75-2-s-20%-AD	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name:	
Vial:	34	Acq. Method Set:	20%qb
Injection #:	1	Processing Method:	xt 2 75 2 s
Injection Volume:	10.00 ul	Channel Name:	254.0nm
Run Time:	60.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 254.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	1/21/2022 2:44:15 PM CST		
Date Processed:	1/21/2022 2:57:49 PM CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	4.884	148173	3.02	16783
2	5.732	4751598	96.98	516764